

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14906730>

INTERACTION BETWEEN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION AND FAMILY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILD'S SPEECH

Tashmurodova Khalima Allaberdiyevna

Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Annotation: *As the child grows up, the need to speak begins to appear in him, - says Farahnoz Begmurodova. - At first, he recognizes the people around him, gradually learns the words and sentences he hears. And when he gets into the language, his vocabulary grows rapidly. Simple words, then simple sentences and full, extended sentences. Dialogic speech occurs in the family, in the circle of parents and siblings. He tries to ask for what he needs, starts communication. Conversations on pre-prepared topics, dramatization methods, dramatization games, and question-and-answer sessions are very useful in developing the speech of preschool children. It should be noted that for a child, an adult is the only means of finding answers to questions, a source of interesting impressions.*

Keywords: *Speech, technology, thought, word, incentive, interactive, child, education, visual, maturation, perception, process.*

Аннотация: *По мере взросления ребенка у него начинает появляться потребность говорить, - говорит Фарахноз Бегмуродова. - Сначала он узнает окружающих людей, постепенно усваивает слова и предложения, которые слышит. А когда он знакомится с языком, его словарный запас быстро растет. Простые слова, затем простые предложения и полные расширенные предложения. Диалогическая речь возникает в семье, в кругу родителей, братьев и сестер. Он пытается попросить то, что ему нужно, начинает общение. Беседы на заранее подготовленные темы, приемы инсценировки, игры-драматизации, сеансы вопросов и ответов очень полезны для развития речи дошкольников. Следует отметить, что для ребенка взрослый – единственное средство поиска ответов на вопросы, источник интересных впечатлений.*

Ключевые слова: *семья, речь, воспитатель, сотрудничество, словарный запас, организация, диалог, диалог, монолог.*

Nowadays, the development of speech among students of an educational institution is one of the urgent problems. Children with speech defects are especially common in preschool education, which is the lower level of educational institutions. In this process, the role of educators and parents in the development of children's speech is great. If the child cannot pronounce any letter correctly, no result can be achieved. Individual work with a child with a speech impediment gives effective results. If a child does not have enough vocabulary, they will not be able to express their opinion. To develop a child's speech, it is necessary to increase his interest in activities. It is necessary to increase the child's interest in nature and to communicate more actively with it, to study its inner experiences. The more vocabulary a child has, the more it affects his psychological development. A child can express his feelings through words. For this, it is necessary for the teachers of the educational institution to encourage children's speech activity. It is also necessary for the teacher to use modern pedagogical technologies for the development of children's speech. Innovative technology develops the child's creative ability, teaches new thinking. By asking the child more colorful pictures, fairy-tale books, and various interesting games, it is possible to increase the vocabulary and reduce any defects in speech. Fairy tales written for children should have interesting content. Children increase their vocabulary by listening to a fairy tale. Thus, coloring books increase the child's visual perception and encourage understanding of the meaning of words. Many aspects of a child's mental maturity develop in connection with speech. In the process of forming speech culture in the child, the use of interactive methods of activities becomes important.

If the teacher uses ICT during his work, he will help to develop the child's oral speech. A child with a speech impediment should be dealt with not only by the educational organization, but also by the father or mother in the family. In the family, it is necessary to create a collection of special colored pictures, interesting story books, and all kinds of toys for the child. In this case, parents should have conversations with the child on various topics, teach the child to freely express his thoughts through games. If the child cannot pronounce the sound combination correctly, it is necessary to teach him to pronounce it together.

REFERENCES

1. ST Xabilova, M Nazarova “MENTAL EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN” Innovative research in modern education 97-99 2023.5.17 <http://aidlix.com/index.php/ca/article/view/651>
2. S Xabilova “EDUCATION OF FUTURE PRESCHOOL TEACHERS IN A MODERN SPIRIT” International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research 3(4) 132-135 2023.4.26 <http://www.researchcitations.com/index.php/ibmscr/article/view/1234>
3. Xabilova, S. (2023). THE PECULIARITY OF FORMING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL-PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE OF EDUCATORS. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(6), 202–204. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/3373>
4. Xabilova, S. T. qizi, & Nazarova, M. (2023). TARBIYA TURLARI VA ULARNING SHAXS KAMOLOTIGA TA’SIRI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 94–96. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/3809>
5. Allaberdiyevna T. K. RELATIONSHIPS OF EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS AND FAMILIES TO THE SCHOOL ON CHILD SPEECH DEVELOPMENT //AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 5. – C. 10-14. <https://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2996-5209>